

EVALUATION OF DIAMETERS OF INHIBITION OF MICROBIAL GROWTH ZONES SILVER NANOPARTICLES

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In recent years, extensive research has been conducted all over the world to develop a technology for the synthesis of rare metal nanoparticles and finished dosage forms based on them using innovative technologies in the pharmaceutical industry.

In view of the effectiveness and practical harmlessness of such materials, great hopes are pinned on their use in medicine.

In particular, the use of drugs containing silver nanoparticles in the treatment of wounds and inflammatory skin diseases deserves special attention. The main reason for this is that these drugs have advantages such as high efficiency, slow development of resistance, low toxicity.

Metal nanoparticles have special physico-chemical properties that differ from the properties of metal ions, they have a therapeutic effect several times greater than the effect of the means in ionic form.

Today, the production of metal nanoparticles by the method of "green synthesis" is one of the most urgent tasks, allowing the production of an unlimited number of non-toxic and inexpensive nanoparticles.

According to doctors, skin diseases occupy the fourth place among the causes of disability, after anemia, tuberculosis and diseases of the sensory organs. In this regard, one of the urgent tasks of the pharmaceutical and medical fields is the development and standardization of medicines for the treatment of wounds of various etiologies.

The effectiveness and safety of the drugs ensure rapid wound healing and rapid recovery of patients' ability to work.

The phytosynthesis of silver nanoparticles was carried out using plant extracts in which biologically active substances, flavonoids, act as an agent that restores silver ions to the nanostate.

The research was carried out in the microbiological laboratory of the Scientific Center for Standardization of Medicines LLC.

The results of the conducted studies showed that the highest efficiency of the test sample was observed in relation to *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6633 -the

diameter of the inhibition zone was 36-40 mm and *Candida albicans* ATCC 885-653 -the diameter of the inhibition zone was 30-38 mm

